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Highlights

- Fault-Tolerant Last Level Cache for CMPs Operating at Ultra-Low Voltage.
- Mechanism that exploits redundancy and reuse to enhance block disabling performance.
- Fault-aware LLC management that maps critical blocks to operative cache entries.
- Detailed evaluation of block disabling techniques in a shared-memory coherent CMP.

A Fault-Tolerant Last Level Cache for CMPs Operating at Ultra-Low Voltage

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Abstract

Voltage scaling to values near the threshold voltage is a promising technique to hold off the many-core power wall. However, as voltage decreases, some SRAM cells are unable to operate reliably and show a behavior consistent with a hard fault. Block disabling is a micro-architectural technique that allows low-voltage operation by deactivating faulty cache entries, at the expense of reducing the effective cache capacity. In the case of the last-level cache, this capacity reduction leads to an increase in off-chip memory accesses, diminishing the overall energy benefit of reducing the voltage supply. In this work, we exploit the reuse locality and the intrinsic redundancy of multi-level inclusive hierarchies to enhance the performance of block disabling with negligible cost. The proposed fault-aware last-level cache management policy maps critical blocks, those not present in private caches and with a higher probability of being reused, to active cache entries. Our evaluation shows that this fault-aware management results in up to 37.3 and 54.2% fewer misses per kilo instruction (MPKI) than block disabling for multiprogrammed and parallel workloads, respectively. This translates to performance enhancements of up to 13% and 34.6% for multiprogrammed and parallel workloads, respectively.

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1. Introduction

For recent CMOS technologies, power density is the main performance limiting factor across most computing segments. Moore's law continues to hold, with a doubling of the number of transistors and integration density in each new process generation, but Dennard scaling no longer applies, and we are not able to keep a constant power density across technology generations. Power budgets prevent us from utilizing all the available transistors, leading to dark silicon [1].

For years, industry has relied on scaling the supply voltage (V_{dd}) to reduce power consumption, but this trend has dramatically slowed since the 90 nm generation because of leakage. Reducing operating voltages to values near the threshold voltage (V_{th}) would minimize leakage and switching power consumption. The resulting power reduction could be used to activate more chip resources and potentially achieve performance improvements [2].

Unfortunately, V_{dd} scaling is limited by the tight margins of the on-chip cache SRAM transistors. Excessive parameter variations in SRAM cells limit the voltage scaling of memory structures to a minimum voltage, $V_{dd_{min}}$, below which SRAM cells may not operate reliably. $V_{dd_{min}}$ usually determines the minimum voltage of the whole processor, and in current technologies is typically of the order of 0.7–1.0 V, when regular 6T SRAM cells are employed.

In the literature, various solutions have been proposed to enable reliable cache operation at low voltages. At the circuit level, the use of larger transistors or more transistors (assist circuitry) improves SRAM cell resilience [3, 4]. The main drawbacks of this approach are the associated increases in area and power consumption. First-level caches in chip multiprocessors (CMPs) occupy little area, and their access time often determines the processor cycle time. Commercial processors, such as the Intel Nehalem family, use robust 8T SRAM cells to build reliable first-level caches, since this represents an affordable overhead [5].

In contrast, last-level caches (LLCs) are usually shared and have larger sizes and associativity, accounting for much of the die area [6]. Hence, for LLCs,
30 minimum-geometry 6T cells are preferred to achieve higher densities.

At the architectural level, fault-tolerant cache designs rely on disabling faulty resources at different granularities [7], or correcting defective bits through either error correction codes (ECCs) [8] or a distributed duplication of blocks [9, 10]. Block Disabling (BD) is a simple technique that disables a cache entry when
35 a defective bit is found [11]. It is already implemented in modern processors to protect against hard faults [6]. However, due to the random distribution of defective cells, the capacity of the cache is rapidly compromised. Complex techniques based on ECCs or the combination of faulty resources are able to rescue more cache capacity, but incur large storage overheads and sometimes
40 require complex remapping that penalizes the cache access latency.

In our work, we have developed a new approach to mitigate the impact of SRAM failures in LLCs due to parameter variations, based on BD but also relying on the underlying structures already present in CMPs. We identify a natural source of on-chip data redundancy that arises because of the replication
45 of blocks in inclusive multi-level cache hierarchies and exploit this redundancy through a smart fault-aware cache management policy.

In this paper, we make the following contributions. First, we provide an evaluation of BD techniques in a shared-memory coherent CMP running parallel and multiprogrammed workloads with a complete and detailed memory model,
50 exploring SRAM cells with different probabilities of failure. Second, we introduce a technique that keeps the tags of the LLC and, therefore, the tracking capabilities of the coherence directory operational. This way, a block not physically stored in the LLC can reside in the private level and be made available to other cores. As an alternative to main memory supply, we set up a cache-to-cache copy
55 service to support code or data sharing (thread migration, operating system, or parallel workloads). Finally, we propose a fault-aware cache management policy that predicts the usefulness of a block based on its use pattern, and guides the allocation of blocks to faulty and non-faulty cache entries, adding no overhead

to the original replacement policy.

60 Our fault-aware cache management policy is able to decrease the LLC misses per kilo instruction (MPKI) by up to 37.3%, with respect to BD, which translates to speedup improvements of 2 to 13% for multiprogrammed workloads. For parallel workloads, the MPKI values decrease by 5 to 54.2%, with respect to BD, for the different SRAM cells considered, improving performance up to 34.6%.

65 This paper extends our previous work [12] in several significant ways: i) a new fault-aware cache management policy aiming at caches operating at low voltages, ii) a detailed implementation of block disabling with operational tags (BDOT) technique, iii) a more realistic SRAM fault model, improving the accuracy of the results, and iv) a more detailed evaluation including multi-programmed
70 workloads and cache capacity/energy analysis.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the problem of process variations and its effect on SRAM cell reliability. Section 3 comments on BD and its impact on large cache structures. In Section 4, we describe how to take advantage of the coherence infrastructure to operate at low V_{dd} . Section 5
75 introduces a fault-aware cache management policy for LLC operating at low voltages. Section 6 describes the methodology. Section 7 presents our evaluation. Section 8 discusses the system impact. In Section 9, we comment on related work, and in Section 10, we outline our conclusions.

2. Process Variations in SRAM cells

80 SRAM structures are especially vulnerable to failures due to process variations, as they are aggressively sized to meet high density requirements, and because of the vast number of cells that comprise on-chip SRAM structures [13]. In particular, intra-die random dopant fluctuations (RDFs) are the main cause of threshold voltage variation [14]. The stochastic nature of the ion implantation
85 process leads to a distribution of V_{th} values across a chip, which reduces the already tight transistor margins. Hence, SRAM structures have a minimum voltage, $V_{dd_{min}}$, to guarantee reliable operation, which is typically of the order

of 0.7–1.0 V in current process generations, when 6T cells are used.

The robustness of SRAM cells under the $V_{dd_{min}}$ range has been extensively
 90 analyzed in the literature [10, 9, 3, 8, 15]. Zhou *et al.* studied six different
 sizes of 6T SRAM cells in 32 nm technology, and their probabilities of failure as
 V_{dd} decreases [4]. According to that study, at 0.5 V, the probability of failure of
 an SRAM cell (P_{fail}) is between 10^{-3} and 10^{-2} . The use of larger cells reduces
 the probability of failure, as non-uniformities average out, increasing read and
 95 write margins and resulting in more robust devices. However, large cells reduce
 the density and increase power and energy consumption.

Table 1 describes the six SRAM cells of Zhou’s study (C1, C2, C3, C4, C5,
 and C6) in terms of their area relative to the smallest cell (C1), and lists the
 percentage of non-faulty entries in caches built from these cells operating at 0.5
 100 V, assuming 64-byte cache entries. An entry is considered faulty if it contains at
 least one defective bit.

As Table 1 shows, less than 10% of the cache entries are non-faulty for the
 small cells C1 and C2 at 0.5 V. If the cache is implemented with the more robust
 C6 cells, however, the percentage of non-faulty cache entries rises to 60%, but at
 105 the cost of a 58% increase in area (relative to C1), and the consequent increase
 in leakage, which is not a suitable option for a large structure such as an on-chip
 LLC.

In this work, we take Zhou’s reliability study as a reference to test our
 proposals on a wide range of failure probabilities. We will only consider C2 to
 110 C6 operating at 0.5 V (our target near-threshold V_{dd}), as at this voltage, a cache
 built with C1 cells would have all its capacity compromised.

Table 1: Area relative to cell C1 and percentage of non-faulty 64-byte entries in a cache
 operating at 0.5 V, for the 6 bit cells introduced in [4].

Cell type	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
Relative area	1.00	1.12	1.23	1.35	1.46	1.58
% non-faulty	0.0	9.9	27.8	35.8	50.6	59.9

Figure 1: Available associativity of a 16-way set associative block disabling cache (64-byte block) made up of cells C6-C1 operating at 0.5 V.

3. Impact of Block Disabling on Large Shared Caches at Ultra-low Voltages

A simple approach to handling hard faults is the disabling of faulty elements. BD deactivates resources at block (cache entry²) granularity: when a fault is detected at a given cache entry, that entry is marked as defective and it can no longer store a cache block [11]. This technique is implemented in modern processors to enable them to tolerate hard faults [6].

BD has also been studied for operation at low voltages because of its easy implementation and low overhead [15]. From the implementation perspective,

²In this work, we differentiate between cache block and cache entry: block refers to the transfer unit, the content *per se*, while entry refers to the physical group of cells that store a block.

only one bit per entry suffices to mark the entry as faulty. The main drawback of this approach is that the amount of capacity dramatically falls when the probability of failure increases, as shown in Table 1. Even if the total count of faulty cells in the cache is less than 1%, the effective cache capacity is strongly
125 affected because of the random distribution of faulty cells. BD results in caches with variable associativity per set, determined by the number and distribution of faults in the cache.

The interaction between BD and a system’s cache organization also plays an important role. Modern commercial processors, such as the Intel Core i7,
130 implement inclusive hierarchies to facilitate coherence management. Inclusive hierarchies require that all the blocks cached in a private cache are also stored in the shared LLC. The coherence information is embedded in the LLC; i.e., the sharing state and a bit vector to represent the current sharers are added to each block. To force inclusion, when a block is evicted from the LLC, explicit back
135 invalidations are required to remove the copies of the private cache blocks, if present (inclusion victims) [16].

Inclusive hierarchies perform poorly when the aggregated size of the private caches is similar to the size of the LLC [17], and BD exacerbates the problem because of the substantial associativity and capacity degradation in the LLC.
140 Figure 1 shows the available associativity in a 16-way set associative cache bank with 64-byte blocks, when built with cells C1-C6 (Table 1) operating at 0.5 V. The number of faulty ways per set follows a binomial distribution $B(n, p)$, where n is the associativity, and p denotes the probability of failure of a cache entry. Figure 1 shows how the associativity degrades as more faulty cells appear
145 on the cache structure. On average, 50% of the ways are faulty if the cache is built with C5 cells, and this percentage rises to 90% when using C2 cells. The associativity loss directly translates to a significant increase in the number of inclusion victims. For instance, the number of invalidations in a cache built with C3 cells is 10 times larger than in a cache implemented with fault-free SRAM
150 cells.

This finding suggests that inclusive hierarchies are not particularly suitable

for systems that implement BD in the presence of a significant number of faults. From the coherence management perspective, however, only directory inclusion is required: blocks present in the private levels have to be tracked only in the shared level tag array, without the need for a replica in the data array [16]. This observation is the basis for the techniques we propose in this paper.

Our proposal has been designed for inclusive memory hierarchies, but most of the proposed ideas could benefit non-inclusive and exclusive hierarchies as well. The objectives of our replacement and promotion algorithms are to assign the non-faulty entries to blocks with reuse and to blocks that are not present in the private caches. On the one hand, these objectives are still valid in a non-inclusive hierarchy; however, their relative importance is different, and our algorithms should consider different priorities for allocation and promotion decisions. On the other hand, our proposal alleviates a specific problem of inclusive hierarchies, such as the need to invalidate a block in a private cache when it is evicted from the shared cache. This problem does not exist in non-inclusive hierarchies, and therefore our proposal is not applicable in this specific aspect.

Note on Figure 1 that, when using cell types C3 and C2, 0.6% and 18.9% of the sets have no operative ways, respectively. To be able to offer a complete comparison with BD, we assume that at least one of the ways in each set is non-faulty, although this is not a requirement for the techniques we present in this paper, and the LLC is able to operate even when all the ways of a set are faulty.

4. Exploiting Inclusive Hierarchies to Enable Ultra-low Voltage Operation: Block Disabling with Operational Tags

The BD scheme simply assumes one extra bit per entry to identify faulty cache entries in the data array (one or more faulty cells). Faulty data entries are excluded from tag search and replacement, involving a net reduction in associativity, and a consequent increase in inclusion victims. From the coherence management perspective, however, tracking blocks in the shared level tag array

suffices to ensure directory inclusion. This is the basis of our previous work, [12], and the starting point of the first technique we propose: *Block Disabling with Operational Tags* (BDOT).

Assuming a two-level inclusive hierarchy, to force directory inclusion, we turn
185 on the tags of faulty entries in the LLC, including them in the conventional operations of search and replacement. The tag of a faulty entry, if valid, tracks a cache block that might be present in the private caches, but that cannot be stored in the shared cache. Enabling the tags of the faulty entries restores the associativity of the shared cache as seen by the first-level private caches,
190 eliminating the problem of the increase in the number of inclusion victims caused by the loss in associativity.

In this situation, two kinds of LLC entries have to be distinguished: tag-only (T), where the associated data entry is faulty and only the tag is stored, and tag-data (D), where the associated data entry is non-faulty and both tag and
195 data are stored. From the implementation perspective, one resilient bit still suffices to indicate whether the entry is faulty or not. The coherence protocol needs to be adapted to this new situation, where a T entry only stores the block tag and directory state. Whenever a request to a block stored in a T entry arrives to the LLC bank, the request needs to be sent to the next level (in this
200 case, the off-chip memory) to recover the block, and the same occurs with dirty blocks, which need to be written back to memory after being evicted from a private cache.

To fully exploit this scheme, no failures should occur in the cells of the tag array. This can be accomplished, for example, by using robust cells (e.g.,
205 increasing the number of transistors per cell) or increasing the strength of the ECC. Tags occupy very little area in comparison to the data array (around 6% for our configuration, see Table 2 in Section 6), and increasing the cell size by 33% (assuming 8T SRAM cells [18]) will only increase the total area of a cache bank by 2%. Since using sophisticated ECCs could increase the access latency of
210 the tag array, while using resilient tag cells involves little overhead, we opt for the latter. This approach is also consistent with prior work [9, 10]. Moreover, many

of today’s CPUs use different cell types for tag and data arrays [19]. Contrary to other proposals, our mechanism works even when all entries of a set are faulty. Contrary to other proposals, our mechanism works even when all entries of a set are faulty. The LLC saves the tags for both faulty and non-faulty entries, maintaining the coherence status of all the blocks, and allowing blocks to be stored in the private levels without the need of a data replica in the shared level. Hence, it is possible to store a block in the private caches even if all the data ways of the corresponding LLC set are faulty.

4.1. *BDOT Limitations*

BDOT, as described above, has two potential limitations, both related to the allocation of blocks to faulty entries.

First, BDOT always forwards requests to blocks allocated to faulty entries to the off-chip memory. However, a block allocated to a faulty entry might be present on-chip, if it is being used by a private cache (L1). This situation is common in parallel workloads, which share data and instructions. In this case, the directory information can be used to orchestrate cooperation among L1 caches. When the directory protocol receives an L1 request to a shared block mapped to a T entry, it forwards the request to one of the sharers of the block, namely, the L1 cache closest to the requester in terms of Manhattan distance. That L1 will serve the block through a cache-to-cache transfer.

Cache-to-cache transfers are already implemented in the baseline coherence protocol for exclusively owned blocks. Hence, no additional hardware is required and a slight modification of the directory protocol suffices to trigger a shared block transfer. So from now on, we assume that BDOT includes this feature.

The second limitation comes from allocating blocks to LLC entries without taking into account their *T* or *D* nature. Unfortunately, this blind allocation can result in heavily reused blocks being attached to faulty entries. Indeed, if a particular block of the LLC is required repeatedly from an L1 cache (i.e., the block shows reuse), any replacement algorithm will tend to protect it, reducing its eviction chances. Thus, if a block with reuse is initially allocated to a *T* entry,

unless replicated in other cores, all L1 cache misses will be forwarded off-chip by the LLC.

In the next section, we introduce a specific allocation and reallocation policy for BDOT caches that differentiates between T and D entries.

5. Fault-aware Cache Management Policy for BDOT Caches

Conventional cache management policies assume that every cache entry can store a block, while BDOT breaks this assumption: each set in an N -way set associative cache contains T entries that store only tags, and D entries that store tags and data. Keeping in mind the main goal of improving the overall LLC performance under BDOT, this section introduces a fault-aware cache management policy that takes into account the distinct nature of T and D entries, and the reuse pattern of the reference stream. In particular, we seek to achieve the following two goals:

1. To allocate blocks that are most likely to be used in the future to D entries.
2. To maximize the amount of on-chip data by giving greater priority (higher chances of being allocated to D entries) to blocks that are not present in private cache levels.

Prior work has shown that *reuse* is a very effective predictor of the usefulness of a given block in the LLC [20, 21]. Reuse locality can be described as follows: lines accessed at least twice tend to be reused many times in the near future, and recently reused lines are more useful than those reused earlier [20]. Therefore, seeking to achieve our first goal, we exploit reuse locality to predict which blocks should be allocated to D entries. With respect to our second goal, a request to a block allocated to a T entry and present in L1 can be serviced through a cache-to-cache transaction, whilst if the block is not present in L1, the request will always be forwarded to the off-chip memory, incurring a penalty in access time and energy. Therefore, it is preferable to dedicate D entries to blocks not available on the L1 caches.

Figure 2: Reuse and inclusion states for a block in LLC. NR, R, C, and NC represent: Non-Reused, Reused, Cached (in L1), and Non-Cached (in L1), respectively. Replacement and coherence transitions are not shown.

270 These goals may be added to any management policy. In this work, we will build on top of a state-of-the-art reuse-based replacement algorithm: Not-Recently Reused (NRR) [20]. Next, we describe the baseline replacement in some depth and then we add awareness of the existence of faulty entries.

5.1. Baseline NRR Replacement Algorithm

275 The NRR algorithm requires four states per LLC block, as depicted in Figure 2. When a block not present in the LLC is requested by the processor (*1st use: L1 request*), it is stored in the L1 and the LLC (to force inclusion), its state being in the LLC NR-C (Non-Reused, Cached). When the block is evicted from the private cache (*L1 eviction*), its LLC state changes to NR-NC (Non-Reused, Non-Cached).
 280 On a new request (*2nd use (reuse): L1 request*), a copy of the block is stored again in L1, and its LLC state is R-C (Reused, Cached). At this point, the block has shown reuse in the LLC and, very likely, it will be reused many times in the near future. Finally, when the block is evicted again from the L1, the state becomes R-NC (Reused, Non-Cached). Subsequent requests and evictions
 285 switch between the R-NC and R-C states.

Having LLC blocks classified this way, the replacement policy can exploit L1 temporal locality and LLC reuse. In an inclusive hierarchy, the replacement of a block in the LLC forces the invalidation of its copies in the private caches, if any, and this usually implies performance degradation, assuming that blocks in L1 are

290 being actively used [17]. Therefore, the highest priority (protection) is given to
 blocks stored in private caches. As a secondary objective, the highest priority is
 given to blocks that have shown reuse in the LLC. Hence, NRR selects victims in
 the following order: NR-NC, R-NC, NR-C, R-C. Reuse recency is taken into account
 by resetting the reuse bit when all the non-cached blocks are marked as reused
 295 (transition from R-NC to NR-NC). This way, more recently reused blocks become
 more protected.

The implementation of NRR only requires one *reuse bit* per block. The
 protection of private copies can be implemented in various different ways [17],
 but one simple solution is to use the presence bit-vector of the coherence directory,
 300 assuming non-silent tag evictions of clean blocks.

(a) Insertion from main memory after LLC (b) Insertion from L1 after L1 eviction (promot-
 ion and demotion).

Figure 3: Insertion and promotion actions for a fault-aware cache management policy example
 in a cache set with two faulty cache entries. Lowercase and capital letters indicate tag and
 data, respectively.

5.2. Reused-based and Fault-aware Management for BDOT Caches

Seeking to guarantee that valuable blocks remain in the LLC, we devise a
 fault-aware management policy by distinguishing between *T* and *D* entries. One
 option is to *promote* blocks by reallocating them from *T* to *D* entries, if needed,
 305 to improve the overall cache performance. The design choices include *where*
 the promoted data comes from and *which* victim is chosen as a target of the
 consequent *demotion*. At the same time, we want to continue exploiting reuse in
 the simple and efficient way offered by an NRR-like replacement algorithm, which

is unaware of faulty entries. Thus, our goal is to design a comprehensive cache
310 management policy, merging reuse exploitation and faulty entry management.
Below, we elaborate on the two mechanisms that are key to achieving this,
namely block insertion/replacement and block promotion/demotion.

5.2.1. Insertion and Replacement of Blocks

On a first insertion (LLC miss), an incoming block has not shown reuse, and
315 hence allocating it to a T entry seems a reasonable idea. Figure 3a shows an
example of a cache block to be inserted in a 4-way cache set with two T entries
(those storing q and r tags) and two D entries (those storing p and s tags and
the corresponding P and S data). A victim is selected among the blocks allocated
to T entries. The baseline replacement policy dictates which of those blocks
320 (Q and R) is selected for replacement. This is equivalent to predicting that the
incoming block X is not going to be reused. If the reuse pattern of the block is
mispredicted, block X should be reallocated to a D entry, to reduce its access
time and transfer energy in future L1 misses. This reallocation will be performed
using the promotion mechanism we detail in the next subsection.

325 Dealing with first insertions this way is very simple but has a clear disad-
vantage, related to the distribution of T and D entries, with respect to the
percentage of reused and non-reused blocks. For example, if the number of T
entries is small, the insertion policy would place considerable pressure on these
scarce entries. Blocks would be unavoidably forced to leave the LLC before
330 having had enough time to show a reuse pattern, even though there are many
available D entries. In an extreme case, when all the entries in a set are D
type, this cache management policy could not be implemented. Solving this
problem is not easy. We explored various adaptive mechanisms in which some D
entries are used as T . However, it is difficult to determine the optimal number
335 of T entries, this being highly dependent on the workload. After carrying out
several experiments (data not shown in Section 7, for the sake of brevity), the
performance returns were disappointing given the required complexity.

Given that our promotion mechanism reallocates reused blocks to D entries

and non-reused ones to T entries (as we will see in the following subsection), we
340 realized that the baseline NRR replacement policy itself suffices to achieve our
initial goals because it protects reused blocks. Since NRR gives lower priority
to non-reused blocks, blocks allocated to T entries will have more chances to
be evicted. This implies that, with a balanced distribution between T and D
entries, an incoming block will have a higher probability of being inserted in
345 a T entry than in a D entry. If the number of T entries in a set is very low,
and even if there are no T entries in a set, the mechanism still works correctly.
NRR periodically resets the reuse bit of those blocks not present in private
caches, so some D entries become replacement candidates with the same priority
as T entries. Hence, the initial insertion does not necessarily have to consider
350 the nature of the entry, and our implementation relies only on the baseline
replacement policy to select the victim block.

5.2.2. Promotion and Demotion of Blocks

A blind allocation of blocks to cache entries may result in valuable blocks (i.e.,
those with reuse) being initially allocated to T entries, and vice versa. However,
355 this undesirable situation can be tracked on the fly through the reuse footprint,
and reversed by swapping a T entry with a D entry: when a block allocated to
a T entry shows reuse, we will *promote* it to a D entry. Promotion involves a
complementary *demotion* of the block stored in the selected D entry.

To select which block is demoted, we also rely on reuse and L1 presence
360 information. Reused blocks should be kept in the LLC, but unlike in the
baseline replacement policy, *block demotion does not involve an LLC tag eviction*.
Furthermore, if the block is present in L1, losing the contents of the LLC is
not critical, because there is at least one on-chip copy of the block, which can
be supplied by a cache-to-cache transaction. Thus, to maximize the amount of
365 on-chip data, the demotion algorithm will select the victim block among those
present in L1. Among the blocks in L1, non-reused ones should have more
chances of being demoted.

Note that the promotion of a block can be performed at two different times:

at reuse detection (i.e., on a second L1 request to a block stored in a T entry) or
 370 after the second eviction from L1 (i.e., on eviction after reuse). Performing the
 promotion after the second request from L1 duplicates the content, as a copy
 of the block is also stored in a private cache, whilst performing the promotion
 after the L1 eviction meets the goal of maximizing the amount of on-chip data.
 Therefore, we opt for the latter and trigger promotions only after L1 evictions,
 375 non-silent block data evictions being necessary.

The promotion/demotion process is illustrated in Figure 3b. When block
 R , which is stored in a T entry, is evicted from the L1 cache and selected for
 promotion (i.e., its reuse bit is set), we select a victim among the demotion
 candidates (P and S in Figure 3b). Once the victim is selected (P in our example),
 380 we swap the cache contents in three steps: ① discard the data entry P , writing
 back the data to memory, if dirty; ② swap p and r tags; and ③ copy the data
 (R) to the available D entry, which was occupied by the demoted block (P).

5.2.3. Summary and Implementation

Figure 4 illustrates the implementation of the aforementioned ideas. The
 385 states of the baseline replacement algorithm shown in Figure 2 are now *superstates*
 split into T and D states. The initial allocation of blocks (*1st use: L1 request*
 in Figure 4) does not take into account the nature of the entry, and it solely
 depends on the victim selection arising from reuse and L1 presence; i.e., it only
 depends on the baseline replacement algorithm. After insertion, blocks will
 390 move along NR-C, NR-NC, R-C, and R-NC superstates as they would do in a cache
 without considering faulty entries.

To guarantee that high value blocks—those showing reuse—remain in the
 LLC, the policy reallocates them from T to D entries when they are evicted
 from the L1 and reside in a faulty LLC entry: R-C-T state. After *L1 eviction*,
 395 blocks in R-C-T trigger a promotion, which results in the transition to an R-NC-D
 state and reallocation to a D entry, with the consequent demotion of another
 block within the set to a T entry. A block being demoted can be in any of the
 superstates, and according to the victim selection algorithm, we first demote

Figure 4: Reuse and inclusion states for a block in LLC with BDOT.

blocks that are present in the private levels, in order to maximize the amount
of data available in the on-chip hierarchy. As a secondary objective, the policy
400 attempts to first demote low priority blocks, that is, those without reuse. In
particular, it selects blocks in the following order: NR-C-D, R-C-D, NR-NC-D, and
R-NC-D.

This reuse-based, fault-aware policy adds no extra storage overhead to the
405 baseline reuse-based replacement policy, as only the bit indicating reuse and the
presence bit vector are needed to orchestrate the replacement and promotion
decisions. Moreover, swapping blocks only requires some extra control logic to
perform the following actions: first, the logic reads the demoted victim and
inserts the promoted block, as for conventional block insertion, and, then, it
410 writes back the tag of the demoted block. Promoting blocks after L1 eviction
implies non-silent eviction of data blocks. This overhead does not affect latency,

as L1 replacements are not in the critical path, and has a negligible impact on energy consumption.

The fault-aware cache management technique here presented could be implemented on top of other replacement algorithms (such as LRU or NRU). We
415 decided to rely on NRR because of its simple, yet efficient implementation, and because it fits the general principles behind our ideas. Finally, and regarding the reallocation from T to D entries and vice versa, other policies are also possible. For example, instead of relying on the reuse information of the blocks, a future
420 use predictor [22] could be utilized to decide which blocks should be allocated to D entries, or a dead block predictor [23] could be used to indicate which blocks may be demoted to T entries, but these solutions add complexity to the cache logic as well as requiring more storage overhead.

6. Methodology

6.1. Overview of the System

425

Our baseline system consists of a tiled CMP, with an inclusive two-level cache hierarchy, where the second level cache or LLC is shared and distributed among the processor cores. Tiles are interconnected by means of a mesh. Each tile has a processor core with a private first level cache (L1) split into instructions and data,
430 and a bank of the shared LLC, both connected to the router (Figure 5). Similarly to most CMP, the write-policy for L1 data caches is write-back because other policies, such as write-through, may collapse the interconnection network [24]. The mesh will have to convoy every single store from the cores to the LLC banks to guarantee content inclusion. The CMP includes two memory controllers
435 located at the edges of the chip. Table 2 shows the parameters of the baseline processor, memory hierarchy, and interconnection network.

We assume it runs at a frequency of 1 GHz with an operating voltage of 0.5 V. Note that the DRAM module voltage is not scaled like the rest of the system, and hence, the relative speed of main memory with respect to the chip increases
440 as the voltage decreases. This model is consistent with prior work [9, 10].

Figure 5: Modeled 8-core CMP.

Our baseline coherence protocol relies on a full-map directory with Modified, Exclusive, Shared, Invalid (MESI) states. We use explicit eviction notification of both shared and exclusively owned blocks. L1 caches are built with robust SRAM cells that can run reliably at low or near-threshold voltages, while LLC data banks are built with conventional 6T SRAM cells and, therefore, they are sensitive to failures [5].

As in previous studies [9, 10], we assume that the LLC tag arrays are hardened by using upsized cells such as 8T [18]. The baseline LLC replacement policy is Not-Recently Used (NRU) [25] extended with private copy protection [17]. We implement this protection by using coherence directory information updated by non-silent L1 block evictions.

6.2. Experimental Set-up

Regarding our experimental set-up, we model the CMP system described in Table 2. We use Simics [26] in combination with GEMS [27] to simulate the on-chip memory hierarchy and interconnection network, and DRAMSim2 [28] to simulate the DDR3 DRAM in detail. To obtain timing, area, and energy consumption, we use the McPAT framework [29] for the on-chip components, and DRAMSim2 for the DRAM module. We extend the Ruby module (GEMS) to simulate the cache swaps in detail in order to take into account their dynamic energy overhead.

Table 2: Main characteristics of the CMP system.

Cores	8, Ultrasparc III Plus, in-order, 1 instr./cycle, single-threaded, 1 GHz at V_{dd} 0.5 V
Coherence protocol	MESI, directory-based (full-map) distributed among LLC cache banks
Consistency model	Sequential
L1 cache	Private, 64 KB data and instr. caches, 4-way, 64 B block size, LRU, 2-cycle hit access time
LLC cache	Shared, inclusive, interleaved by line address, 1 bank/tile, 1 MB/bank, 16-way, 64 B block size, NRU replacement 8-cycle hit access time (4-cycle tag access + 4-cycle data access)
Memory	2 memory controllers, located at the edges of the chip; 1333 MHz DDR3 2 channels, 8 Gb/channel, 8 banks, 8 KB page size, open page policy; raw access time 50 cycles
NoC	Mesh, 2 virtual networks (VNs): requests and replies; 2 virtual channels per VN; 16-byte flit size 1-cycle latency hop, 2-stage routing

We use a set of 20 multiprogrammed workloads built as random combinations of the 29 SPEC CPU 2006 applications [30], with no special distinction between integer and floating point programs. Each application appears on average 5.5 times with a standard deviation of 2.5. Programs were run on a real machine until completion with the reference inputs. Hardware counters were used to locate the end of the initialization phase. Every multiprogrammed mix was run for as many instructions as the longest initialization phase, and a checkpoint was created at this point. We then run cycle-accurate simulations including 300 million cycles to warm up the memory hierarchy and 700 million cycles for data collection.

We also include a selection of shared-memory parallel applications from PARSEC [31] with a significant memory footprint ($MPKI_{LLC} \geq 1.0$) when running the *sim-large* input in the baseline system: **canneal** ($MPKI_{LLC} = 4.3$), **ferret** (1.6), **streamcluster** (1.0), and **vips** (1.2). We proceed in a similar

475 way to that used for multiprogrammed workloads³ and run 300 million cycles to
warm up the memory structures once the parallel phase has started, and then
collect statistics for 700 million cycles.

One challenge for analyzing fault mitigation techniques is the large set of
required simulations. Running all workloads and simulated models combinations
480 for a single fault map can lead to wrong results, as other authors have de-
scribed [32, 33]. For example, if all the faults affect to the most/least frequently
accessed cache sets, the observed speed-up would be much lower/higher than in
reality.

To address this issue, we rely on statistical sampling to generate random
485 fault maps and run Monte Carlo experiments to guarantee a 5% margin of error
with a confidence level of 95% [34]. In other words, the number of samples is
increased as necessary to reach the target margin of error within the desired level
of confidence. For our workloads, simulated models, metrics, margin of error
and confidence level, each point of the design space has to be simulated between
490 20 and 30 times, each one with a different fault map. We pick the 5% margin
of error and the 95% confidence level as a good trade-off between simulation
time and accuracy, increasing both has a large impact in the required number
of simulations. To ensure all simulations have similar numbers of faults but at
different locations, we compute the faultiness of each memory cell randomly and
495 independently of other cells [35, 36]. Finally, we consider that the number and
location of faulty cells do not change during workload execution.

7. Evaluation

This section evaluates the effectiveness of the proposed BDOT management
technique for LLC caches in terms of MPKI, adding up the misses in all LLC

³We observed that no OS activity appeared when our parallel applications were run and
the ratio of CPU utilization between the different threads was practically constant across the
simulations.

500 banks and dividing by the aggregated instruction count of all cores. Later, in Section 8, we analyze the impact on system performance, area, and energy.

To assess the effectiveness of our proposals, we include several additional configurations. First, as an upper bound in performance, a robust cache built with *unrealistically robust cells* (Robust); i.e., cells that operate at ultra-low
505 voltages with neither failures nor power or area overheads, which corresponds to a perfect unattainable solution. Then, we also include *block disabling* (BD), as our proposal emerges from it. Finally, we add results for *word disabling* (WD) [10]. Word disabling is a more complex technique that combines consecutive faulty cache entries to recreate fully functional ones, at the cost of reducing the
510 cache capacity. Section 9 presents a comprehensive discussion of this and other techniques versus our proposals.

In summary, we consider the following configurations:

- **Robust**: reference system; the LLC is built with unrealistically robust cells. All data are presented with respect to this system.
- 515 • **BD**: system implementing block disabling, as presented in Section 3, with NRU replacement.
- **BDOT-NRU**: system implementing block disabling with operational tags, as presented in Section 4, with NRU replacement.
- **BDOT-NRR**: system implementing BDOT with NRR replacement, as
520 presented in Section 5.1.
- **BDOT-NRR-FA**: system implementing BDOT with fault-aware NRR replacement, as presented in Section 5.2.
- **WD**: system implementing word disabling with NRU replacement [10].

As in the case of NRR, the NRU implementation also includes private
525 copy protection. Our detailed results include multiprogrammed workloads (the 20 SPEC CPU 2006 mixes) and parallel workloads (the 4 selected PARSEC applications), for the five cell types considered (C6, C5, C4, C3, and C2).

Figure 6: Normalized MPKI (average for SPEC mixes) with respect to Robust for the different proposals and cell types. Average MPKI for Robust: 5.09.

7.1. Multiprogrammed Workloads

Figure 6 shows the LLC MPKI results for the multiprogrammed workloads.

530 BD is a valid solution for a cache with few defective entries, like one built with C6 cells, where the average MPKI penalization is 23.9%. However, this penalization increases rapidly with the number of faulty entries, reaching 136% for C2. Using the tags of the defective LLC entries to keep the coherence state of blocks stored in L1 allows BDOT-NRU to incur fewer MPKI than BD for C2, 535 but it does not offer any advantage (the MPKI value increases) for the rest of the cells.

To differentiate and quantify the benefit of a reuse-based replacement and our fault-aware cache management policy, we first implement NRR on top of BDOT (BDOT-NRR), without taking into account the nature of cache entries 540 (faulty or non-faulty). This naive implementation offers a slight improvement with respect to BDOT-NRU for all cell types, but it is still worse than BD, except for C2, as in the case of BDOT-NRU. The explanation for this behavior is the blind allocation of blocks to entries, without taking into account whether the entry can store only the tag (T) or both the tag and the data (D). Allocating a

545 block that shows reuse to a T entry implies that all the requests to that block
are forwarded to the next level (in this case, off-chip). Besides, due to the
reused-based policy, this block will remain in the defective entry of the LLC,
protected by the replacement algorithm. However, blocks with reuse allocated
to D entries are also protected from replacement, and that explains why the
550 relative differences between BDOT-NRR and BDOT-NRU are larger when using
larger cells (i.e., with less faults, like C6 and C5).

BDOT-NRR-FA addresses this issue, adding the information of defective
entries to the cache management policy. The penalization in terms of MPKI is
14.6%, 15.1%, 16%, 18.3%, and 37.3% lower than with BD for C6, C5, C4, C3,
555 and C2, respectively. If we compare BDOT-NRR-FA with BDOT-NRR, there
are 20% fewer MPKI, irrespective of the cell type, demonstrating the goodness
of the design.

Regarding WD, although there are significant differences in terms of the
number of defective entries among the cell types considered (Table 1), the MPKI
560 for the different configurations is almost constant. Two reasons explain this
behavior: i) a single defective cell forces the entry to be classified as faulty, and
ii) the number of defective cells per entry is usually small (three on average
for the smallest cell: C2 [37]) and, therefore, very often blocks are successfully
stored by combining two consecutive entries. Thus, the average number of ways
565 per set in our system when implementing WD is eight across the different cell
configurations. Compared to BD, WD obtains better results when the average
number of defective entries is greater than half, which is the case of cells C4, C3,
and C2, as shown in Table 1. BDOT-NRR-FA lowers the MPKI with respect
to WD by 20%, 16.1%, 8.5%, and 3.4%, for C6, C5, C4, and C3, respectively.
570 WD only beats BDOT-NRR-FA in caches with a high number of defective cells
(C2, where on average 90% of the entries are faulty). However, BDOT-NRR-FA
requires no additional overhead, whilst WD requires additional storage and logic
to reconstruct blocks.

Figure 7: Normalized MPKI (average for PARSEC) with respect to Robust for the different proposals and cell types. Average MPKI for Robust: 2.01.

7.2. Parallel Workloads

575 Figure 7 shows the relative LLC MPKI for the parallel workloads, with respect to the baseline. As with multiprogrammed workloads, BDOT-NRR-FA has a lower average MPKI than BD and non fault-aware implementations of BDOT. In particular, BDOT-NRR-FA improves MPKI with respect to BD by 5%, 5%, 9.6%, 19.2%, and 54.2% on average for C6, C5, C4, C3, and C2, 580 respectively. Comparing with the multiprogrammed workloads, the relative MPKI numbers shown in Figure 7 are larger, moving away from the Robust system to a greater extent for all cell types, even for the winning alternatives (WD and BDOT-NRR-FA). But it is worth noting that the absolute MPKI values for the parallel applications considered are low (Section 6), which makes 585 the relative increases appear more substantial.

Upon closer examination of the results, we can make some interesting observations. Figure 8 shows the LLC MPKI analysis per application for the different cell types. BD is better than plain BDOTs (BDOT-NRU, BDOT-NRR) in C6-C3 cells (C3 in `canneal` is an exception), while in cell C2 the trend clearly reverses. 590 On the contrary, BDOT-NRR-FA is better than BD in most cases, being `vips`

the only exception (cells C6-C3), and giving very noticeable reductions in the smallest cell C2. For *vips*, BDOT-NRR-FA only beats BD in C2 because its image processing algorithm shows very little reuse with a small working set. In such non-demanding environment, BD can store the *vips* working set.

595 Finally, the costly WD shows a similar tendency to that observed with multi-programmed workloads, with a relatively constant performance independently of the cell type. In this case, BDOT-NRR-FA beats WD when using C6 or C5 (12.7% and 6.6% lower MPKI values, respectively), but it cannot reach WD performance for C4, C3, or C2 (5.5%, 12.4%, and 33.3% higher MPKI values, 600 respectively).

8. System Impact

This section analyzes the impact of our proposals on the system in terms of performance, area, and energy consumption. As in the previous section, we present results relative to the Robust system and compare with the BD and WD 605 mechanisms.

8.1. Performance

Figure 9 shows the performance relative to the robust cell for both multiprogrammed and parallel workloads.

For multiprogrammed workloads (Figure 9a), performance follows the same 610 trend as MPKI, BDOT-NRR-FA being the best design option except in the case of C2 cells, for which WD outperforms BDOT-NRR-FA by 2.2%. In particular, BDOT-NRR-FA shows a performance degradation with respect to the Robust reference system of 1.3%, 2%, 3.4%, 4.3%, and 6.9% for C6, C5, C4, C3, and C2, respectively, or, in other words, a performance improvement with respect to BD 615 of 2%, 2.2%, 2.7%, 3.6%, and 13.1%.

As in the case of multiprogrammed workloads, speedup in parallel application performance (Figure 9b) also follows the same trend as in the MPKI results, with a notable exception. For C3, BDOT-NRU and BDOT-NRR perform slightly

(a) canneal.

(b) ferret.

(c) streamcluster.

(d) vips.

Figure 8: Per-application normalized MPKI (PARSEC) with respect to Robust for the different proposals and cell types. Average MPKIs for Robust: 4.26, 1.59, 1.0 and 1.19, for canneal, ferret, streamcluster, and vips, respectively.

Figure 9: Normalized speedup (average) with respect to Robust for the different proposals and cell types.

better than BD on average, while in Figure 7, the average MPKI value with these
620 techniques was higher than with BD. As we already mentioned, the LLC MPKI
for the parallel applications in the baseline system is small (Section 6), and small
MPKI increases with respect to this system appear relatively large in Figure 7.
Nevertheless, for C3, `streamcluster` has a dramatic speedup degradation with
BD. This is due to the large number of back invalidations to L1 blocks to force
625 directory inclusion (inclusion victims). Specifically, in this application, the
number of invalidations to L1 blocks decreases 20 times when implementing
BDOT. The MPKI numbers are similar, but the number of instructions executed
differ considerably. For this application, we observe a performance improvement
of 6.1% when using BDOT-NRU (6.2% for BDOT-NRR), with respect to BD.

630 On average, BDOT-NRR-FA shows a similar performance to BD for C6 and
C5, where the performance degradation with respect to the reference system is
2.2% and 2.9%, respectively, and for C4, C3, and C2, the performance is better,
by 1.8%, 7.1%, and 34.6%, respectively. BDOT-NRR-FA and WD have similar
performance (within 1%), except for in the case of C2, for which WD achieves a
635 3.1% better performance.

In summary, BDOT-NRR-FA is an excellent choice for caches with different

numbers of defective entries, as it achieves as good performance as more complex fault-tolerant techniques without adding any extra storage overhead to the cache.

8.2. Area and Energy

Figure 10: Normalized EPI (average) with respect to Robust for the different proposals and cell types.

640 Larger SRAM cells are less likely to fail, but at the cost of larger areas and higher power consumption. Even the largest cell considered by Zhou’s study (C6), which requires a 41.1% larger area than C2, is far from reaching fully functional performance: 40.1% of the cache entries are faulty at 0.5 V (Table 1).

Our fault-aware mechanism has a minimal impact on area. Only two extra
 645 bits suffice to implement BDOT-NRR-FA: one bit marks entries as defective (as in BD), and the other one stores the replacement policy (i.e., NRR) information. Thus, no extra storage overhead is added compared to the BD system.

Minimizing area helps to reduce energy in the LLC. Signals traveling smaller distances require less dynamic power for switching, and, most importantly, small
 650 cells consume less static power. To estimate the sub-threshold current, I_{sub} , causing the static consumption, we assume that I_{sub} is directly proportional to the transistor width of the cells considered, and estimate it with respect to C2 [4]. For the unrealistically robust cell, we assume that it is the same size as

C2, but with a null probability of failure. Energy consumption also includes the
655 dynamic overhead of LLC block swaps and L1 clean data eviction required by
the fault-aware BDOT policy. Finally, we account for both the on-chip power
and the off-chip DRAM power.

Figure 10 shows the energy per instruction (EPI) for all the systems and
cell types considered, both for multiprogrammed (Figure 10a) and parallel
660 (Figure 10b) workloads, with respect to a system implemented with robust cells
at 0.5 V, distinguishing between on-chip and off-chip consumption.

For BD, the 2.4-fold higher MPKI for C2 escalates the off-chip DRAM traffic,
and in turn, significantly increases off-chip DRAM EPI for both multiprogrammed
and parallel workloads. On average, BDOT-NRR-FA results in a 5.4%, 5.8%,
665 6.8%, 8.2%, and 20.4% lower overall EPI than BD for C6, C5, C4, C3, and
C2, respectively, for the multiprogrammed workloads. In the case of parallel
workloads, the EPI of BDOT-NRR-FA is within 2% of BD for C6, C5, and C4,
and 7.4% and 26.8% lower for C3 and C2, respectively.

Regarding WD, the results show the same trend as performance, namely,
670 BDOT-NRR-FA EPI results are 7.5%, 9.8%, 7%, and 4% lower for C6, C5, C4,
and C3, respectively, when considering multiprogrammed workloads, while for
parallel workloads, the EPI values of the two techniques are very similar for C6
and C5, but BDOT-NRR-FA cannot achieve the efficiency of WD for the other
cell configurations.

675 The energy results shown above do not consider any block power gating
technique [38]. Assuming a more aggressive approach, where fine-grained block
power gating is affordable [39], the benefits of BD-based techniques in terms
of power and energy will be enhanced, as faulty entries do not consume static
power during operation. Applying this technique, the EPI with BDOT-NRR-FA
680 would be 6.2%, 6.7%, 7.2%, 6.3%, and 5.5% lower for the multiprogrammed
workloads than the EPI values in Figure 10 with C6, C5, C4, C3, and C2 cells,
respectively. The same tendency is observed in the parallel workload results.

Figure 11 compares the EPI values with BD and BDOT-NRR-FA when
implementing block power gating with those obtained with WD. We observe that

685 for multiprogrammed workloads all the cell configurations achieve significant improvements in terms of EPI with respect to WD, and in the case of parallel workloads, only the C2 configuration is not able to reach the WD efficiency.

(a) Multiprogrammed workloads.

(b) Parallel workloads.

Figure 11: Normalized EPI (average) with respect to word disabling, when implementing fine-grained block power gating.

9. Related Work

Conventional 6T SRAM cells fail to operate reliably in the near-threshold regime, as the ratio constraints for read stability and writability of transistors cannot be guaranteed, especially in view of V_{th} variations. Prior proposals to mitigate the impact of SRAM cell failures due to parameter variation at ultra-low voltages can be categorized into circuit and architectural solutions.

Circuit solutions include methods that improve the bit cell resilience by increasing its size [4], or by adding assist/spare circuitry [18, 3]. Increasing the cell size or the number of transistors per cell comes at the cost of significant increases in the SRAM area (lower density) and power consumption. Since the LLC accounts for much of the die size, increasing its area (e.g., ST SRAM cells [3] double the area of the SRAM structure) is not a design option.

Architectural solutions include redundancy through ECCs, disabling techniques, and duplication mechanisms. Our proposal fits in this category.

ECCs are extensively employed to protect designs against soft errors. Some

studies have extended the use of ECCs to protect against hard errors when running at ultra-low voltages [40, 8]. ECCs are usually optimized to minimize their storage requirements, at the cost of complex logic to detect and correct errors. Thus, the ability to detect and correct more errors comes at the cost of increasing the complexity of the decoding stage, or the storage requirements of the check bits [8]. Our proposal is orthogonal to the use of ECCs to provide more functional entries (or any other technique that increases the number of functional entries), as it adapts seamlessly to the amount of functional and non-functional data entries in the cache.

Regarding BD [11], Lee *et al.* examine performance degradation of disabling cache lines, sets, ways, ports, or the complete cache in a single processor environment [7]. Ladas *et al.* implement a victim cache to compensate for the loss in associativity [15]. Our approach also relies on BD, but does not require any additional structures.

Ghasemi *et al.* propose the use of heterogeneous cell sizes, in order that when operating at low-power, ways or sets made of smaller SRAM cells are deactivated if they start to fail [41]. Khan *et al.* propose a mixed-cell memory design, where a small portion of the cache is implemented with robust cells, which store dirty cache blocks, and the remainder with non-robust cells [19]. They modify the replacement policy to guide the allocation of blocks based on the type of request (load or store). Zhou *et al.* combine spare cells, heterogeneous cell sizes, and ECCs into a hybrid design to improve on the effectiveness obtained by any single technique alone [4]. In contrast to these techniques, we do not rely on the existence of robust ways and we guide the allocation of blocks to faulty or operational LLC entries based on their reuse.

The granularity at which capacity is disabled could be finer, though this would add complexity to cache accesses. Word disabling tracks defects at word-level granularity, combining two consecutive cache entries into a single fault-free entry, halving both associativity and capacity [10]. Abella *et al.* propose to bypass faulty subentries rather than disable full cache lines, but this technique is suitable only for the first-level cache, where accesses are word wide [42].

Palframan *et al.* follow a similar approach, patching faulty words from other
735 microprocessor structures, such as the store queue or the miss status holding
register [43]. Ferrerón *et al.* compress cache blocks to fit them in faulty entries,
allowing the utilization of 100% of the cache entries [37]. More complex schemes
couple faulty cache entries using a remapping mechanism [9, 44, 45]. They group
collision-free cache entries (from the same or different cache banks) relying on
740 the execution of a complex algorithm and structures to store all the mapping
strategy. Re-mapping mechanisms add a level of indirection to the cache access
(increasing its latency), and the combination of cache entries to recreate a cache
block adds complexity. Besides, several cache accesses are needed to obtain a
fault-free cache block, increasing the energy consumption and/or the block access
745 latency. Unlike the aforementioned proposals, we do not add any additional
structures or re-mapping mechanisms, only minor changes to the coherence
protocol and replacement policy.

In the context of ultra-low voltages, Keramidas *et al.* use a PC-indexed spatial
predictor to orchestrate the replacement decisions among fully and partially
750 usable entries in first-level caches [46]. We based our allocation predictions on
reuse patterns, which simplifies the hardware, and we do not consider the use of
partially faulty entries.

Regarding the implementation of our techniques, it is worth referring to
the work of Jaleel *et al.* [17]. In inclusive hierarchies, the private caches filter
755 the temporal locality and hot blocks (i.e., blocks being actively used by the
processor) are degraded in the replacement algorithm of the LLC, eventually
being evicted. They address this problem by protecting blocks present in the
private caches and preventing their replacement in the LLC through several
techniques, including: sending hints to the LLC, identifying temporal locality
760 via early invalidation, and querying the private caches about the presence of
blocks. We also protect private copies in all the replacement policies considered
(including the baseline one), in our case by using the coherence information and
assuming non-silent evictions of clean blocks.

Albericio *et al.* base replacement decisions on block reuse locality [20]. They

765 propose the *Not-Recently Reused* (NRR) algorithm, which protects blocks present
in the private caches and blocks that have shown reuse in the LLC. Their simple
yet efficient implementation achieved better performance than more complex
techniques such as RRIP [47]. Our proposal uses NRR as the base replacement
policy.

770 10. Summary and Conclusions

Voltage reduction has been the primary driver to reduce power during recent
decades, but ultra-deep-submicron technologies have suddenly stopped this
trend because of problems with leakage and stability. Manufacturing-induced
parameter variations make SRAM cells unstable at lower voltages, meaning that
775 they require a minimum voltage to operate reliably. SRAM cell failures can be
tolerated by deactivating faulty cache entries. This technique is called Block
Disabling (BD) and requires only one bit per tag. Unfortunately, as the number
of defective entries increases, so does performance degradation, and the energy
saved from decreasing V_{dd} does not compensate for the extra energy required
780 for the additional main memory accesses.

The reduction in associativity and capacity experienced by inclusive LLCs
extended with BD has two specific drawbacks in multicore systems. First,
the number of inclusion victims in private L1 caches increases. Second, the
MPKI values also grow, increasing LLC miss latency and main memory energy
785 consumption.

To cope with the first problem, we propose Block Disabling with Operational
Tags (BDOT), which uses robust cells to implement the LLC tag array. BDOT
enables some cache blocks to be only in private levels by simply tracking their
tags (T entries), and extends the existing cache-to-cache coherence service to
790 clean blocks. Thus, with regard to inclusion victims, the LLC associativity is
fully restored. BDOT requires a small amount of extra control, and it adds
no storage overhead to BD (the bit that marks operative entries sufficing to
distinguish between LLC T and D entries). Any replacement algorithm may work

with BDOT, and we have tested NRU and NRR, two low-cost state-of-the-art
795 proposals for LLCs.

After the last copy L1 eviction of a block tracked by a T entry, a future
reference to this block will involve an off-chip access, even though we know
that reuse chances are high. Hence, we tackle the second problem from the key
observation that we can preserve the data cached on-chip by exchanging the
800 valuable, just evicted T entry block (promotion), for an L1-present D entry block
(demotion). Furthermore, if all blocks allocated to D entries lack L1 copies, we
can still resort to demotion, losing effective on-chip capacity, assuming that an
incoming L1 block showing reuse (second L1 replacement) is more valuable than
any older block allocated to a D entry. We have implemented these ideas in
805 BDOT-NRR-FA, the fault-aware version of BDOT that selects for demotion a
 D entry victim block that has a backup copy in L1 (first criterion), and has
not shown reuse in the LLC (second criterion). Compared to a BDOT LLC
using NRR replacement, BDOT-NRR-FA improves performance and energy
efficiency with no area overhead, because the bits per block required, namely for
810 the presence vector, operative entry, and reuse are required, respectively, by the
coherence mechanism, BD, and conventional replacement.

We tested our proposals against a wide range of multiprogrammed and
parallel workloads under different P_{fail} situations. Our best proposal, BDOT-
NRR-FA, beats BD, results in up to 37.3% and 54.2% lower MPKI values for
815 multiprogrammed and parallel workloads, respectively. These decreases translate
to performance improvements of 13% and 34.6%, respectively. Regarding energy
use, our proposal decreases EPI by between 5.4% and 20.4% for multiprogrammed,
and between 2% and 26.8% for parallel workloads. The largest savings come
from LLCs with the most faulty cells, and gains are consistent across programs,
820 making our proposal very suitable for the operation of multicore LLCs at low
voltages for current and future technology nodes.

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